

Some Applications to Nonlinear Dispersive Waves

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Abstract

The general theory is developed for studying changes of a wave train governed by nonlinear partial differential equations. The slow dispersion of nonlinear water waves is studied by the general theory. The averaged Lagrangian is then calculated from the Stokes expansion for periodic wave-trains in water of arbitrary depth. This Lagrangian can be used for the various applications.

Introduction

In nonlinear problems of dispersive waves, it is well known that solutions take the form of an infinitely long, periodic wave train. Stokes waves and cnoidal waves are early examples of water waves.

In the work of Whitham, an averaging technique was introduced to determine the slow variation in time and space of a nonlinear wave train. These slowly varying wave trains occur in two main problems. Firstly, it is known from linear theory that an arbitrary initial disturbance disperses into a slowly varying wave train. Secondly, it is often important to consider wave trains entering a slowly varying medium.

Examples are, water waves over a sloping beach or plasma waves propagating through a slowly varying magnetic field.

Crossing swells, consisting of near-cnoidal wave trains

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Two cnoidal waves meet at cross sea

Boundary Control of Long Waves in Nonlinear Dispersive Systems

Variational Principle for Water Waves

The equations of irrotational water waves

$$\phi_{xx} + \phi_{yy} = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad -h_0 < y < \eta, \tag{1}$$

$$\eta_t + \phi_x \eta_x - \phi_y = 0, \quad \text{on} \quad y = \eta, \tag{2}$$

$$\phi_x h_{0x} + \phi_y = 0, \quad \text{on} \quad y = -h_0. \tag{3}$$

The first equation (1) is the Laplace's equation and the last two equations (2) and (3) are the kinematic boundary conditions

$$\phi_t + \left\{ (\phi_x)^2 + (\phi_y)^2 \right\} / 2 + gy = 0, \quad \text{on} \quad y = \eta, \tag{4}$$

which is the condition that the pressure be constant on the free surface $y = \eta(x, t)$, if the surface tension is neglected.

These follow completely from the *Hamilton's variational principle*

$$\delta \iint L dx dt = 0, \tag{5}$$

with the Lagrangian $L = L(\phi, \eta)$, denoted by

$$L = \int_{-h_0}^{\eta} \left\{ \phi_t + \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \phi)^2 + gy \right\} dy, \tag{6}$$

where y is the vertical coordinate, x is the horizontal coordinate, $\phi(x, y, t)$ is the velocity potential, $y = \eta(x, t)$ is the free surface, $y = -h_0$ is the rigid bottom, and g is the acceleration due to gravity. The general theory of dispersion can now be applied to this system with the Lagrangian given by (6) and follows the standard pattern. The y -dependence does not give any trouble, because it is integrated out in (6).

The Averaged Lagrangian for Stokes Waves

In this section, the equations for slow variation in the amplitude, wave-number, etc. will be established for arbitrary depth. There is no explicit exact solution for the uniform wave train; it is calculated by the Stokes expansion in powers of amplitude. The theory for slowly varying wave trains will be worked out in the same way. The analysis is carried out for the case of one horizontal space dimension.

First, we take the form for the uniform periodic solution of the water wave equations so that the wave-number vector $\underline{\kappa}$, frequency w , pseudo wave-number vector $\underline{\beta}$ and pseudo frequency γ are all constants. Second, for the non-uniform wave trains, the form of the solution is generalized slightly so that the quantities (κ, w, a) and (β, γ, b) are all taken to be slowly varying functions of space and time instead of constant parameters.

Uniform Periodic Solution

The uniform periodic solution of the water wave equations take the form

$$\eta = N(\theta), \theta = \kappa x - wt, \phi = \beta x - \gamma t + \Phi(\theta, y), \tag{7}$$

where κ, w, β and γ are constant parameters with the wave number vector $\underline{\kappa}$ and the frequency w . The phase function θ will be normalized so that it increased by 2π in one period, where π is a fixed positive constant. Physically, $\underline{\beta}$ is the mean velocity. Mathematically, $\underline{\beta}$ and γ act like a pseudo wave-number vector and frequency in ϕ corresponding to the real wave number vector $\underline{\kappa}$ and frequency w in θ .

Non-Uniform Wave Trains

For non-uniform wave-trains, the form of the solution is generalized slightly to

$$\eta = N(\theta), \quad \phi = \psi + \Phi(\theta, y), \tag{8}$$

$$\theta_x = \kappa \quad \theta_t = -w, \tag{9}$$

$$\psi_x = \beta, \quad \psi_t = -\gamma, \tag{10}$$

and the quantities $\kappa, w, a, \beta, \gamma, b$ are all taken to be slowly varying functions of space and time instead of constant parameters.

The General Method of Whitham

The averaged Lagrangian $\bar{L}$ of the Lagrangian L over the wavelength:

$$\bar{L}(\kappa, w, a; \beta, \gamma, b) = (1/2P) \int_0^{2P} L d\theta, \quad (11)$$

from the uniform wave-train solution. Then for the non-uniform wave-train, where the scale is large compared with one wavelength, the averaged variational principle

$$\delta \int \bar{L} dx dt = 0, \quad (12)$$

is used, with κ, w, β and γ are restricted by equations. (9) and (10).

Variation in Amplitude a

For a small change δa in a , the first variation is

$$\delta J[a, \delta a] = \int \int \delta a \frac{\partial L}{\partial a}(\kappa, w, a; \beta, \gamma, b) dx dt, \quad (13)$$

to vanish for all admissible functions δa and this implies that

$$\partial L / \partial a = 0, \quad (14)$$

by the usual continuity argument. Equation (14) is the *Euler's equation*.

Variation in Mean Height b

For a small change δb in b , the first variation is

$$\delta J[b, \delta b] = \int \int \delta b \frac{\partial L}{\partial b}(\kappa, w, a; \beta, \gamma, b) dx dt, \quad (15)$$

to vanish for all admissible functions δb and this implies

$$\partial L / \partial b = 0, \quad (16)$$

by the usual continuity argument. Equation (16) is the *Euler's equation*.

Variation in Phase Function θ

For a small change $\delta \theta$ in θ , the first variation is

$$\delta J[\theta, \delta \theta] = \int \int \delta \theta \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial w} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \kappa} \right) \right\} dx dt. \quad (17)$$

to vanish for all admissible function $\delta \theta$ and this implies that

$$-\partial L_w / \partial t + \partial L_\kappa / \partial x = 0, \quad (18)$$

by the usual continuity argument. Equation (18) is the Euler's equation.

Variation in Phase-Like Function ψ

For a small change $\delta \psi$ in ψ ; the first variation is

$$\delta J[\psi, \delta \psi] = \int \int \delta \psi \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \gamma} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \beta} \right) \right\} dx dt, \quad (19)$$

to vanish for all admissible function $\delta\psi$ and this implies that

$$-\partial L_\gamma / \partial t + \partial L_\beta / \partial x = 0, \tag{20}$$

by the usual continuity argument. Equation (20) is the Euler’s equation.

Consistency Conditions

The system is completed by eliminating θ in (9), and eliminating ψ in (10) to give the consistency conditions

$$\partial \kappa / \partial t + \partial w / \partial x = 0, \tag{21}$$

$$\partial \beta / \partial t + \partial \gamma / \partial x = 0, \tag{22}$$

Linear Theory

While developed specifically for nonlinear waves, this theory provides a new general treatment of linear dispersive waves. In the linearized theory of one-dimensional water waves, equations (7) becomes

$$\eta = N(\theta), \theta = \kappa x - wt, \quad N(\theta) = b + a \cos(\pi\theta / P), \tag{23}$$

$$\phi = \beta x - \gamma t + \Phi(\theta, y), \quad \Phi = A_1 \cosh([\pi\kappa / P][h_0 + y]) \sin(\pi\theta / P), \tag{24}$$

where h_0 is the undisturbed depth, b is the mean height, a is the amplitude.

Lagrangian

From (6), (23) and (24) the Lagrangian L is

$$L = \int_{-h_0}^{N(\theta)} \left\{ -(\gamma + w\Phi_\theta) + \frac{1}{2} [(\beta + \kappa\Phi_\theta)^2 + \Phi_y^2] + gy \right\} dy \tag{25}$$

$$= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) (h_0 + N) + \frac{1}{2} gN^2 - \frac{1}{2} gh_0^2 - (w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \int_{-h_0}^N \Phi_\theta dy + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_0}^N (\kappa^2 \Phi_\theta^2 + \Phi_y^2) dy,$$

If the total mean depth is $\tilde{h}$ and the function $M = M(\theta)$ by the relations

$$\tilde{h} = h_0 + b, \quad M = a \cos(\pi\theta / P), \quad \eta = N = b + M, \quad b = (1 / 2P) \int_0^{2P} \eta d\theta \tag{26}$$

so that $h_0 + \eta = h_0 + N = h_0 + b + M = \tilde{h} + M$, a function of θ , and we have the relations

$$\left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) (h_0 + N) = \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) (\tilde{h} + M), \quad \frac{1}{2} gN^2 = \frac{1}{2} gb^2 + gbM + \frac{1}{2} gM^2,$$

there relation

$$\begin{aligned} -(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \int_{-h_0}^N \Phi_\theta dy &= -\frac{\pi}{P} (w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \int_{-h_0}^{N(\theta)} A_1 \cosh\left(\frac{\pi\kappa}{P}[h_0 + y]\right) \cos\frac{\pi\theta}{P} dy \\ &= -\frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} A_1 \sinh\left(\frac{\pi\kappa}{P}[h_0 + N]\right) \cos\frac{\pi\theta}{P} \\ &= -\frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} A_1 \sinh\left(\frac{\pi\kappa}{P}[\tilde{h} + M]\right) \cos\frac{\pi\theta}{P}, \end{aligned}$$

and the relation

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_0}^N (\kappa^2 \Phi_\theta^2 + \Phi_y^2) dy \\
 &= \frac{A_1^2}{2} \int_{-h_0}^N \left\{ \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2}{P^2} \cos^2 \frac{\pi \theta}{P} \cosh^2 \left(\frac{\pi \kappa}{P} [h_0 + y] \right) + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2}{P^2} \sin^2 \frac{\pi \theta}{P} \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi \kappa}{P} [h_0 + y] \right) \right\} dy \\
 &= \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 A_1^2}{8P^2} \int_{-h_0}^N \left\{ \cosh \left(\frac{2\pi \kappa}{P} [h_0 + y] \right) + 1 \right\} \left[1 + \cos \frac{2\pi \theta}{P} \right] \\
 & \quad + \left[\cosh \left(\frac{2\pi \kappa}{P} [h_0 + y] \right) - 1 \right] \left[1 - \cos \frac{2\pi \theta}{P} \right] dy \\
 &= \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 A_1^2}{4P^2} \int_{-h_0}^N \left\{ \cosh \left(\frac{2\pi \kappa}{P} [h_0 + y] \right) + \cos \frac{2\pi \theta}{P} \right\} dy \\
 &= \frac{\pi \kappa A_1^2}{8P} \sinh \left(\frac{2\pi \kappa}{P} [h_0 + N] \right) + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 A_1^2}{4P^2} (h_0 + N) \cos \frac{2\pi \theta}{P} \\
 &= \frac{\pi \kappa A_1^2}{8P} \sinh \left(\frac{2\pi \kappa}{P} [\tilde{h} + M] \right) + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 A_1^2}{4P^2} (\tilde{h} + M) \cos \frac{2\pi \theta}{P}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the Lagrangian L becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) (\tilde{h} + M) + \frac{1}{2} g b^2 + g b M + \frac{1}{2} g M^2 - \frac{1}{2} g h_0^2 \\
 & \quad - \frac{(w - \beta \cdot \kappa)}{\kappa} A_1 \sinh \left(\frac{\pi \kappa}{P} [\tilde{h} + M] \right) \cos \frac{\pi \theta}{P} \\
 & \quad + \frac{\pi \kappa A_1^2}{8P} \sinh \left(\frac{2\pi \kappa}{P} [\tilde{h} + M] \right) + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 A_1^2}{4P^2} (\tilde{h} + M) \cos \frac{2\pi \theta}{P}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Averaged Lagrangian

Since the averaged Lagrangian $\square\square\square$ is defined by

$$L(\kappa, w, a, \beta, \gamma, b) = (1/2P) \int_0^{2P} L d\theta, \tag{28}$$

by using the Lagrangian L from (25), (27), the averaged Lagrangian $\square\square\square$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 \square &= \frac{1}{2P} \int_0^{2P} \int_{-h_0}^{N(\theta)} \left\{ -(\gamma + w \Phi_\theta) + \frac{1}{2} [(\beta + \kappa \Phi_\theta)^2 + \Phi_y^2] + g y \right\} dy d\theta \\
 &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2} g b^2 - \frac{1}{2} g h_0^2 + \frac{1}{4} g a^2 + \frac{\pi \kappa A_1^2}{16P^2} \int_0^{2P} \sinh \left(\frac{2\pi \kappa}{P} \left[\tilde{h} + a \cos \frac{\pi \theta}{P} \right] \right) d\theta \\
 & \quad - \frac{(w - \beta \cdot \kappa)}{2P \kappa} A_1 \int_0^{2P} \sinh \left(\frac{\pi \kappa}{P} \left[\tilde{h} + a \cos \frac{\pi \theta}{P} \right] \right) \cos \frac{\pi \theta}{P} d\theta,
 \end{aligned}$$

Then the simplified averaged Lagrangian $\square\square\square$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \square &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \frac{1}{4}ga^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})A_1}{\kappa} \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{8P^2}\right) \frac{\pi \kappa a}{2P} \cosh \frac{\pi \kappa \tilde{h}}{P} \\ &\quad + \frac{\pi \kappa A_1^2}{8P} \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{P^2}\right) \sinh \frac{2\pi \kappa \tilde{h}}{P} \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Variation in A_1 :

For a small change δA_1 in A_1 , $\partial L / \partial A_1 = 0$, and it gives

$$\frac{\pi \kappa A_1}{4P} \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{P^2}\right) \sin \frac{2\pi \kappa \tilde{h}}{P} = \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{8P^2}\right) \frac{\pi \kappa a}{2P} \cosh \frac{\pi \kappa \tilde{h}}{P}.$$

Simplifying, we get

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} \left\{ \frac{(1 + \pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2 / (8P^2))}{(1 + \pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2 / P^2)} \right\} \frac{2a \cosh(\pi \kappa \tilde{h} / P)}{2 \sinh(\pi \kappa \tilde{h} / P) \cosh(\pi \kappa \tilde{h} / P)} \\ &= \frac{a(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa \sinh(\pi \kappa \tilde{h} / P)} \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{8P^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{P^2} + \dots\right) \\ &= \frac{aw}{\kappa \sinh(\pi \kappa \tilde{h} / P)}, \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

because, in the linear theory, the mean height $b = 0$, and the mean velocity $\underline{\beta} = \underline{0}$. By letting (30) in (29), the simplified averaged Langrangian $\square$ given by (29) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \square &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \frac{1}{4}ga^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} \frac{aw}{\kappa \sinh(\pi \kappa h_0 / P)} \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{8P^2}\right) \frac{\pi \kappa a}{2P} \cosh \frac{\pi \kappa h_0}{P} \\ &\quad + \frac{\pi \kappa}{8P} \frac{a^2 w^2}{\kappa^2 \sinh^2(\pi \kappa_0 / P)} \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2 \kappa^2 a^2}{P^2}\right) 2 \sinh \frac{\pi \kappa h_0}{P} \cosh \frac{\pi \kappa h_0}{P} \\ &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \frac{1}{4}ga^2 - \frac{\pi a^2 w^2 \cosh \frac{\pi \kappa h_0}{P}}{2P \kappa \sinh \frac{\pi \kappa h_0}{P}} + \frac{\pi a^2 w^2 \cosh \frac{\pi \kappa h_0}{P}}{4P \kappa \sinh \frac{\pi \kappa h_0}{P}} \\ &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \frac{1}{4}ga^2 \left(1 - \frac{\pi w^2}{P g \kappa \tanh(\pi \kappa h_0 / P)}\right) \\ &\approx \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 + \frac{1}{4}ga^2 \left(1 - \frac{\pi w^2}{P g \kappa \tanh(\pi \kappa h_0 / P)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

As expected, changes in mean velocity $\underline{\beta}$ and mean heigh b uncouple from the wave motion and take $b = \beta = \gamma = 0$ to obtain the usual linear theory. Then, the averaged Lagrangian is

$$L = \frac{1}{4} g a^2 \left(1 - \frac{\pi w^2}{P g \kappa \tanh(\pi \kappa h_0 / P)} \right) \tag{31}$$

The Stokes Expansion

The expansion from the Fourier series

$$N(\theta) = b + a \cos \frac{\pi \theta}{P} + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n \cos \frac{n \pi \theta}{P}, \tag{32}$$

and

$$\Phi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_n}{n} \cosh \left(\frac{n \pi \kappa}{P} [h_0 + y] \right) \sin \frac{n \pi \theta}{P}, \tag{33}$$

and it is clear that the expansion (33) for Φ satisfies the Laplace’s equation given by $\Phi_{xx} + \Phi_{yy} = 0$, and it also satisfies the boundary condition $\partial \Phi / \partial y = 0$ on the bottom $y = -h_0$. The mean heigh b and the amplitude a are the fundamental coefficients in the solution. The other coefficients a_n and A_n are determined in terms of them by satisfying the free-surface conditions (2) and (4). In the solution of these nonlinear relation by successive approximations, it becomes clear that a_n and A_n are $O(a^n)$.

The Lagrangian for Periodic Wave-Train

First, from (6), (7), we can put the Lagrangian L in the form

$$\begin{aligned} L \square &= \int_{-h_0}^{N(\theta)} \left\{ -(\gamma + w \Phi_{\theta}) + \frac{1}{2} [(\beta + \kappa \Phi_{\theta})^2 + \Phi_y^2] + g y \right\} dy \tag{34} \\ &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) (h_0 + N) + \frac{1}{2} g N^2 - \frac{1}{2} g h_0^2 - (w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \int_{-h_0}^N \Phi_{\theta} dy + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_0}^N (\kappa^2 \Phi_{\theta}^2 + \Phi_y^2) dy, \end{aligned}$$

If the total mean depth is $\tilde{h}$ and the function $M = M(\theta)$ by the relations.

By letting

$$\tilde{h} = h_0 + b, \quad M = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos \frac{n \pi \theta}{P}, \quad a_1 = a, \quad \eta = N = b + M, \quad b = \frac{1}{2P} \int_0^{2P} \eta d\theta, \tag{35}$$

so that $h_0 + \eta = h_0 + N = h_0 + b + M = \tilde{h} + M$, a function of θ , and the relations

$$\left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) (h_0 + N) = \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) (\tilde{h} + M), \quad \frac{1}{2} g N^2 = \frac{1}{2} g b^2 + g b M + \frac{1}{2} g M^2,$$

the relation

$$\begin{aligned}
 -(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \int_{-h_0}^N \Phi_\theta dy &= -\frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_n}{n} \sinh\left(\frac{n\pi\kappa}{P}[h_0 + N]\right) \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{P} \\
 &= -\frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_n}{n} \sinh\left(\frac{n\pi\kappa}{P}[\tilde{h} + M]\right) \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{P},
 \end{aligned}$$

and the relation

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_0}^N (\kappa^2 \Phi_\theta^2 + \Phi_y^2) dy \\
 &= \frac{\pi\kappa}{4P} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} A_r A_{n-r} \left\{ \frac{1}{(n-2r)} \sinh\left(\frac{[n-2r]\pi\kappa}{P}[\tilde{h} + M]\right) \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{P} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{n} \sinh\left(\frac{n\pi\kappa}{P}[\tilde{h} + M]\right) \cos \frac{(n-2r)\pi\theta}{P} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The Lagrangian L becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)(\tilde{h} + M) + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 + gbM + \frac{1}{2}gM^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 \\
 &\quad - \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_n}{n} \sinh\left(\frac{n\pi\kappa}{P}[\tilde{h} + M]\right) \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{P} \\
 &\quad + \frac{\pi\kappa}{4P} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} A_r A_{n-r} \left\{ \frac{1}{(n-2r)} \sinh\left(\frac{[n-2r]\pi\kappa}{P}[\tilde{h} + M]\right) \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{P} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{n} \sinh\left(\frac{n\pi\kappa}{P}[\tilde{h} + M]\right) \cos \frac{(n-2r)\pi\theta}{P} \right\}. \tag{36}
 \end{aligned}$$

Averaged Lagrangian for Periodic Wave-Trains

Using the Lagrangian (34) or (36), the averaged Lagrangian $L = \int_0^{2P} L d\theta / (2P)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= \frac{1}{2P} \int_0^{2P} \int_{-h_0}^{N(\theta)} \left\{ -(\gamma + w\Phi_\theta) + \frac{1}{2}[(\beta + \kappa\Phi_\theta)^2 + \Phi_y^2] + gy \right\} dy d\theta \tag{37} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2P} \int_0^{2P} \left\{ \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)(h_0 + N) + \frac{1}{2}gN^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 - (w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \int_{-h_0}^N \Phi_\theta dy \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_0}^N (\kappa^2 \Phi_\theta^2 + \Phi_y^2) dy \right\} d\theta \\
 &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2 + gb\right) \frac{1}{2P} \int_0^{2P} M d\theta
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{g}{4P} \int_0^{2P} M^2 d\theta - \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa(2P)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_n}{n} \int_0^{2P} \sinh \left(\frac{n\pi\kappa}{P} [\tilde{h} + M] \right) \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{P} d\theta \\
 & + \frac{\pi\kappa}{(4P)(2P)} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \sum_{r=1}^{n-1} A_r A_{n-r} \left\{ \frac{1}{(n-2r)} \int_0^{2P} \sinh \left(\frac{[n-2r]\pi\kappa}{P} [\tilde{h} + M] \right) \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{P} d\theta \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{1}{n} \int_0^{2P} \sinh \left(\frac{n\pi\kappa}{P} [\tilde{h} + M] \right) \cos \frac{(n-2r)\pi\theta}{P} d\theta \right\}. \tag{38}
 \end{aligned}$$

Simplified Averaged Lagrangian

The averaged Lagrangian L (38) can be put in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 L & = \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2} g b^2 - \frac{1}{2} g h_0^2 + \frac{1}{4} g a_1^2 + \frac{1}{4} g a_2^2 - \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa})}{\kappa} (\mu_1 A_1 + \mu_2 A_2) \\
 & + \tilde{\kappa} \left(\frac{1}{2} \mu_{11} A_1^2 + \mu_{12} A_1 A_2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu_{22} A_2^2 \right) + O(a^4), \tag{39}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\tilde{\kappa} = \pi\kappa / P$ and $\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_{11}, \mu_{12}, \mu_{22}$ are the expressions denoted by

$$\mu_1 = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\kappa} a_1 \cosh \tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{4} \tilde{\kappa}^2 a_1 a_2 \sinh \tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{16} \tilde{\kappa}^3 a_1^3 \cosh \tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h}, \tag{40}$$

$$\mu_2 = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\kappa} a_2 \cosh 2\tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{4} \tilde{\kappa}^2 a_1^2 \sinh 2\tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h}, \quad \mu_{12} = \frac{1}{4} \tilde{\kappa} a_1 \cosh 3\tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h}, \tag{41}$$

$$\mu_{11} = \frac{1}{4} \sinh 2\tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{4} \tilde{\kappa}^2 a_1^2 \sinh 2\tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{4} \tilde{\kappa} a_2, \quad \mu_{22} = \frac{1}{8} \sinh 4\tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h}. \tag{42}$$

Variation in A_1 and A_2

From the averaged Lagrangian L given by (39), for a small change δA_1 in A_1 , and a small change δA_2 in A_2 , $L_{A_1} = 0, L_{A_2} = 0$, and then

$$\mu_{11} A_1 + \mu_{12} A_2 = (\kappa \tilde{\kappa})^{-1} (w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \mu_1, \quad \mu_{12} A_1 + \mu_{22} A_2 = (\kappa \tilde{\kappa})^{-1} (w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) \mu_2.$$

By using Cramer’s rule,

$$A_1 = \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) (\mu_1 \mu_{22} - \mu_2 \mu_{12})}{\kappa \tilde{\kappa} (\mu_{11} \mu_{22} - \mu_{12}^2)},$$

$$A_2 = \frac{(w - \underline{\beta} \cdot \underline{\kappa}) (\mu_2 \mu_{11} - \mu_1 \mu_{12})}{\kappa \tilde{\kappa} (\mu_{11} \mu_{22} - \mu_{12}^2)}.$$

The Simplified Form of the Averaged Lagrangian becomes

$$\square = \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 \right) \tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2} g b^2 - \frac{1}{2} g h_0^2 + \frac{1}{4} g a_1^2 + \frac{1}{4} g a_2^2$$

$$-\frac{(\pi/P)^2(w-\underline{\beta}\cdot\underline{\kappa})^2}{4\tilde{\kappa}T}\left\{a_1^2-\left(\frac{3}{4}+T^2\right)\tilde{\kappa}^2a_1^4-\frac{(3-T^2)}{2T}\tilde{\kappa}a_1^2a_2+(1+T^2)a_2^2\right\}+O(a^4), \tag{43}$$

where $T = \tanh(\tilde{\kappa}\tilde{h}) = \tanh(\pi\kappa\tilde{h}/P)$ and terms order a^4 have been neglected. The Quantities $(\underline{\beta}, \gamma, b)$ and a_2 are $O(a^2)$ so that lowest-order approximation corresponding to the usual linear theory is

$$L = -\gamma h_0 + (ga_1^2/4)(1 - (\pi/P)^2 w^2 (g\tilde{\kappa})^{-1} \coth(\tilde{\kappa}h_0) + O(a^2)). \tag{44}$$

(The term $-\gamma h_0$ does not contribute in the final equations and could be omitted.)

The variation of $\square\square\square$ with respect to a_1 , $(\partial L / \partial a_1 = 0)$, gives usual linear dispersion relation:

$$w^2 = w_0^2(\tilde{\kappa}) + O(a^2), \quad w_0^2(\tilde{\kappa}) = (P/\pi)^2 g\tilde{\kappa} \tanh(\tilde{\kappa}h_0). \tag{45}$$

In view of this, terms of order $\{(w^2/w_0^2)-1\}a^2$ will not be need in (43) and it becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \square &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \frac{1}{4}ga_1^2\left\{1 - \frac{(\pi/P)^2(w-\underline{\beta}\cdot\underline{\kappa})^2}{g\tilde{\kappa}T}\right\} + \frac{1}{4}ga_2^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{4}\left(\frac{\pi}{P}\right)^2\frac{(w-\underline{\beta}\cdot\underline{\kappa})^2}{\tilde{\kappa}T}\left\{\left(\frac{3}{4}+T^2\right)\tilde{\kappa}^2a_1^4 + \frac{(3-T^2)}{2T}\tilde{\kappa}a_1^2a_2 - (1+T^2)a_2^2\right\} + O(a^4) \\ &\approx \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \frac{1}{4}ga_1^2\left\{1 - \frac{(\pi/P)^2(w-\underline{\beta}\cdot\underline{\kappa})^2}{g\tilde{\kappa}T}\right\} \\ &+ \frac{1}{4}g\left\{\left(\frac{3}{4}+T_0^2\right)\tilde{\kappa}a_1^4 + \frac{(3-T_0^2)}{2T_0}\tilde{\kappa}a_1^2a_2 - T_0^2a_2^2\right\} + O\left\{a^4, \left(\frac{w^2}{w_0^2}-1\right)a^2\right\}, \end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

where $T = \tanh(\tilde{\kappa}\tilde{h}), T_0 = \tanh(\tilde{\kappa}h_0), \tilde{\kappa} = \pi\kappa/P$. The variation of $\square\square\square$ with respect to a_2 , (that is $\partial\square/\partial a_2 = 0$), now gives the relation $a_2 = (3 - T_0^2)\tilde{\kappa}a_1^2 / (4T_0^3)$.

Final Form of the Averaged Lagrangian

Substituting the value of a_2 in (46), using a_2 the averaged Lagrangian in the final form is

$$\begin{aligned} \square &= \left(-\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2\right)\tilde{h} + \frac{1}{2}gb^2 - \frac{1}{2}gh_0^2 + \frac{1}{2}E\left\{1 - \frac{(\pi/P)^2(w-\underline{\beta}\cdot\underline{\kappa})^2}{g\tilde{\kappa}\tanh(\tilde{\kappa}\tilde{h})}\right\} \\ &+ \frac{1}{2}E^2\left\{1 - \frac{\tilde{\kappa}^2D_0}{g\tanh(\tilde{\kappa}h_0)}\right\} + O(E^3), \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

where $E = ga_1^2/2 = ga^2/2$, and $D_0 = (16T_0^6 + 13T_0^4 - 6T_0^2 + 9) / (8T_0^3)$. The expression (47) is the final form of the averaged Lagrangian and as a function of the two triads $(\underline{\kappa}, w, a)$ and $(\underline{\beta}, \gamma, b)$ (It is often convenient to use E , which is proportional to the energy density, as a variable in place of a).

Nonlinear Dispersion Relation

The variation of ω with respect to a , (or E), gives the nonlinear dispersion relation

$$\frac{(\pi/P)^2 (\omega - \beta \cdot \underline{\kappa})^2}{g \tilde{\kappa} \tanh(\tilde{\kappa} \tilde{h})} = 1 + \frac{2 \tilde{\kappa}^2 D_0 E}{g \tanh(\tilde{\kappa} h_0)} + O(E^2), \quad (48)$$

where $\tilde{\kappa} = \pi \kappa / P$. The relation (48) depends on β and b , (through $\tilde{h} = h_0 + b$), as well as on E .

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Averaged Lagrangian (48) agrees with the result of Whitham who considered the case of one horizontal space dimension and the period of the phase variable θ is 2π . I also expect that Whitham system to be studied, analytically and numerically, the formation of n^{th} horizontal space dimension in nonlinear dispersive waves.

Acknowledgements

I wish to express my sincere gratitude to Rector Dr Win Naing, Dagon University for giving me a permission to undertake this paper. I would like to record my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Thein Aung, Head of Department of Mathematics, Dagon University for his kind permission to carry out this paper. I am deeply indebted to Professor Dr Hla Hla Kyi, Department of Mathematics, Dagon University, for all valuable guidance, helpful advice and supervision.

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